

Concurrent Validity of the PlayerMaker IMU to Measure Key Physical Performance Metrics in Elite Female Football

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Declaration

I confirm that i) that while registered as a Masters by Research Candidate at the University of the West of Scotland, I have not been enrolled as a student at any other institution of higher education, ii) that this thesis does not contain any material that has been previously submitted for an academic award, and iii) that this work is solely the result of my own efforts, except where acknowledged.

Abstract

Inertial measurement units (IMU) are an alternative method to Global positioning systems (GPS) comprising of powerful accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers which can be used indoors and outdoors as they do not require a satellite connection to capture data. PlayerMaker (PM) is a foot mounted IMU which is used to capture locomotor activities in football such as distance covered, peak velocity, and high-speed change of direction. The key difference between PM and GPS is the higher sampling rate; GPS typically have a sampling frequency ranging from 1-20 Hz, whereas PM has a more powerful sampling frequency of 1000 Hz. In team sports, GPS is the 'gold standard' method for monitoring player load during training and competitions, as their validity has been extensively reported within sports literature. Therefore, the overarching aim of this research is to determine the validity of the PM IMU to measure key performance metrics in elite female footballers.

This study measured PM against a valid and reliable GPS (Catapult, Playertek) device during an aerobic performance test and a series of linear and change of direction running drills, within elite female footballers. The findings from this study found PM to significantly underestimate all parameters in comparison to GPS with a poor to good relationship shown between devices. PM was shown to underestimate peak velocity during a 20 m linear sprint (mean difference [95% CI] = -0.48 m/s [-0.66 m/s, -0.38 m/s]), and peak acceleration during a 5 m linear acceleration (mean difference [95% CI] = -1.32 m/s² [-1.72, -0.94]). PM was also shown to underestimate acceleration (mean difference [95% CI] = -0.92 m/s² [-1.37, -0.48] to -1.25 m/s² [-1.90, -0.61]) and deceleration (mean difference [95% CI] = -3.00 m/s² [-3.58, -2.42] to -2.05 m/s² [-2.60, -1.52]) during a 505 COD test, as well as total distance during a 1 km TT (mean difference [95% CI] = -23 m [-35.50, -11.70]). Additionally, a poor to good relationship was reported for all measures between devices (*ICC* < 0.81). The findings from this research suggest PM is acceptable for measuring distance covered and peak velocity during a linear sprint, despite underestimating these values, as good agreement was found between devices (CV = 1.36% and 2.21%, respectively). However, caution should be taken when measuring high speed actions like accelerations and decelerations as poor agreement was found (CV = 9.29%-13.93%). Future research should look to incorporate PM into game scenarios to validate PM during competitive match play and standardise research and validation protocols.

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List of Abbreviations

&: And

%: Percent

CI: Confidence Intervals

cm: Centimeters

COD: Change of Direction

CV: Coefficient of Variation

GPS: Global Positioning System

HSR: High-Speed Running

VHSR: Very High-Speed Running

Hz: Hertz

ICC: Intra-Class Correlation Coefficient

IMU: Inertial Measurement Unit

kg: Kilograms

km/h: Kilometers per hour

km: Kilometers

LoA: Limits of Agreement

m/s²: Meters per second squared

m: Meters

PM: PlayerMaker

SAFT90: Soccer-Specific Aerobic Field Test

SD: Standard Deviation

SEE: Standard Estimate of Error

SEM: Standard Error of Measurement

SWC: Smallest Worthwhile Change

TT: Time Trial

Chapter 1: Introduction

In recent years, elite team sports have increasingly relied on the use of wearable technologies that provide important data on athletes' physical outputs. Data tracking is essential for coaches and sports scientists to manage player load, optimise training, and mitigate injury risks in high-performance sports like football (Theodoropoulos *et al.*, 2020). Various tracking systems have been used in team sports including Global Positioning Systems (GPS); Local Positioning Systems; and Inertial Measurement Units (IMU). These devices are used to report metrics such as distance, velocity, accelerations and decelerations (Clubb *et al.*, 2022), which coaches can use to assess the physical demands of training and competitive games as well monitor athlete readiness.

The accuracy of such devices, particularly in elite sports settings, is critical. Data provided will be dependent on the integrated technology within each device with most typically containing an accelerometer, magnetometer, and a gyroscope (Torres-Ronda *et al.*, 2022). GPS systems are typically worn on the upper back using a purpose made vest and have been the gold standard in external load monitoring for several years, due to their validity for use in team sports (Scott *et al.*, 2016). However, GPS devices have been suggested to be limited by their lower sampling frequency (1–20 Hz) (Scott *et al.*, 2016), specifically when measuring velocity at high speeds, which may reduce their reliability in tracking rapid movements and changes of direction. In contrast, IMU's are less commonly used in performance tracking in professional sports and have limited research to validate their use in an elite setting. PlayerMaker (PM), is a foot mounted IMU system, which offers a higher sampling rate (1000 Hz) than GPS, which could potentially provide greater data accuracy, particularly in dynamic sports such as football. Unlike GPS, PM is worn on the athlete's feet via a silicone strap (Barret *et al.*, 2013) and allows for further data collection relating to the athlete's kicking profile and how often they touch the ball. Despite this promising increase in athlete data, limited research exists to validate the use of IMU's in elite team sports.

The global rise of women's football highlights the need for performance tracking technology and research specific to female athletes. More than 60 million women and girls are expected to participate in organised football by 2026 (FIFA, Women's Football Member Associations Survey Report, 2019), however, female athletes continue to remain underrepresented within sports science research (Costello *et al.*, 2014; Bruinvels *et al.*, 2017; Emmonds *et al.*, 2019; Cowley *et al.*, 2021). The underrepresentation of female athletes within sports science research makes applying an evidence-based approach to female training challenging, plus physiological and biomechanical differences between male and female athletes further justifies the need for greater research within the female population. Differences have been reported between male and female footballers in areas such as

distance covered, High-speed running (HSR), and peak velocity (Bradley *et al.*, 2014) as well as lower power output and force production reported in female athletes (Mirkov *et al.*, 2020; Hallam & Amorim, 2022). These differences justify the importance for PM to be validated at measuring performance at different velocities using appropriate testing methods.

This study aims to evaluate the validity of PM for measuring key performance metrics in elite female football players. This study will focus on metrics such as total distance, peak velocity, acceleration, and deceleration, and seeks to determine the applicability of PM in accurately monitoring the performance of female athletes.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Physiological and match-demands of football

Historically, physiological and match demands in football have predominantly been studied in male footballers (Randell *et al.*, 2020). However, more recently with the use of GPS, match characteristics and physiological demands have been considered in females. Female players have been demonstrated to cover total distances of 9-12 km (Andersson *et al.*, 2010; Krstrup *et al.*, 2010; Turner (2016); Mara *et al.*, 2017), with average heart rates reported to be between 84-86% of the maximum heart rate (Andersson *et al.*, 2010; Krstrup *et al.*, 2010). Published data conveys female players can cover anywhere between 1-3 km of HSR distance and 200-850 m of sprinting distance (Andersson *et al.*, 2010; Mohr *et al.*, 2008; Mara *et al.*, 2017) depending on position (see *Table 1*). Positional differences in running distance have been measured in female footballers, Panduro *et al.* (2021) found fullbacks and midfielders covered greater total distance than central defenders. HSR (total distance covered >15 km/h) and very high-speed running (total distance covered >18 km/h) was greater for fullbacks, midfielders, and forwards than central defenders, and central defenders recorded lowest sprint distances (distance covered >25 km/h).

Due to physiological differences between sexes in terms of females reportedly having lower maximal aerobic capacity, power, and speed (Diaz-Canestro *et al.*, 2022; Mirkov *et al.* 2020), It is important speed and velocity thresholds are taken into consideration when measuring performance in female footballers. Typically, HSR and sprinting are recorded as 15.1-18 km/h and 18.1-25 km/h, respectively (see *Table 1*) (Andersson *et al.*, 2010; Mohr *et al.*, 2008; Panduro *et al.*, 2021). However, Bradley & Vescovi (2014), recommend that velocity thresholds used to define HSR and sprinting in female football players should be 15-16 km/h and 20 km/h, respectively. This is due to female players consistently recording lower values for HSR and sprinting during matches, and lowering these thresholds would maximise measurement device's ability to capture the values. This is supported by research performed in elite sprinters as Mirkov and colleagues (2020) demonstrated that female sprinters have been shown to generate less force than males when accelerating due to females having a proportionally lower volume of muscle mass.

Investigations of repeat sprint profiles suggests that female players complete 4–6 repeat sprint bouts per game, with 3 sprints per bout and 4–7 seconds between each repeat sprint (Gabbett & Mulvey, 2008; Mara *et al.*, 2017). Mara and colleagues (2017) also highlight that female players perform 423 (± 126) accelerations ($\geq 2 \text{ m/s}^{-2}$) and 430 (± 125) decelerations ($\leq -2 \text{ m/s}^{-2}$) per match. Additionally, the mean and maximum distance per high intensity effort was reported as 1–4 m and 2–8 m respectively (Mara *et al.*, 2017), which is relatable to similar research from Datson *et al.*

(2017) who reports 76% and 95% of all sprints are covered between 0-5 m and 0-10 m, respectively. These findings suggest that most high intensity efforts in female football are covered over very short distances which will account for the high number of accelerations and decelerations reported, and the number of accelerations and at different intensities (based on the start and final velocity) varied according to player position (Mara *et al.*, 2017). As elite football demands players to have strong endurance capacity and repeatedly perform high speed runs along with COD, as well as being crucial that there is a sufficient volume of research determining the demands of female football, it is vital that devices used to monitor these metrics are valid and reliable to provide accurate data players and coaches.

Table 1. Physical & Physiological Characteristics of Female Football

Author/Year	Country	Level	Age (years)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Speed threshold (km/h)	TD (km)	HSR distance (m)	Sprint distance (m)
Andersson <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Sweden + Denmark	Senior National Team	27 ± 1	168.2 ± 1.5	61.0 ± 1.4	HSR > 15 Sprint > 25	9.9 ± 1.8	1530 ± 100	256 ± 57
Choi & Joo (2022)	South Korea	WK League	27.8 ± 3.9	165.7 ± 3.1	58.5 ± 5.4	HSR > 19 Sprint > 23	9.5 ± 0.8	361.5 ± 122.6	110.2 ± 84.3
Griffin <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Australia	A-League	25.7 ± 3.1	167.5 ± 7.7	61.3 ± 6.2	HSR > 16 Sprint > 20	8.70 ± 0.28	608.5 ± 68.8	306.3 ± 56.3
Krustrup <i>et al.</i> (2005)	Denmark	Danish Women's League	24 (19 – 31)	167 (156 – 180)	58.5 (49.0 – 70.7)	HSR > 18 Sprint > 25	10.3 (9.7 – 11.3)	1310 (710 – 1700)	160 (50 – 280)
Sausaman <i>et al.</i> (2019)	USA	NCAA Division I	20.6 ± 1.0	163.5 ± 13.3	62.1 ± 7.1	HSR > 15 Sprint > 18 Max Sprint > 25	9.49 ± 3.00	1014 ± 118	428 ± 70
Scott <i>et al.</i> (2020)	USA	NWSL	24 ± 4	168 ± 6	63 ± 5	HSR > 19 Sprint > 22.5	10.68 ± 6.15	398 ± 153	162 ± 69

2.2 Player Load Monitoring

For many years GPS has been used in football and other team sports as the criterion method of tracking players movement with their validity well documented within literature (Scott *et al.*, 2016). Foot-mounted IMUs are relatively new to the sport-related data collection market with limited research confirming their validity for use in elite team sports. In football, training load can generally be separated into two variables: internal and external training load. While internal training load refers to physiological parameters such as heart rate or lactate thresholds, external training load depicts players overall physical activities such as HSR or number of accelerations. Assessment of both internal and external training load is important for player load management and GPS has proven to be a valid and reliable means of collecting data of players' physical outputs (Scott *et al.*, 2016).

PlayerMaker (PM) is a foot-bound IMU that monitors various external load metrics such as high-speed running, and accelerations and is designed to precisely monitor football-specific movements. Despite this, there is an insufficient volume of data to confirm the validity of PM to monitor velocity movements in team sports. Meanwhile, as women's football continues to grow exponentially, there is an increased demand for scientific data to be produced that is specific to female athletes. Martinez-Lagunas *et al.* (2014) conveys a lack of experimental research relating to training loads, recovery capacity, and player characteristics within female footballers. Developing research and knowledge within these areas could hugely improve player performance and enhance the development of women's football.

2.2.1 Global Positioning Systems (GPS)

The use of technology and player tracking devices in football has increased largely over the last decade as teams continually seek to gain a competitive advantage. Since their introduction to field-based sports in 2006 (Aughey, 2011), GPS have become vitally important for monitoring player load and interpreting data to optimise performance and to identify and reduce risk of injury.

A typical GPS unit consists of tri-axial accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers to measure movement across multiple axes (Theodoropoulos *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, GPS uses satellite navigation systems to detect signals omitted from available satellites to the device located on the player. The rate at which GPS captures data depends on the sampling frequency of the device. Therefore, a device measuring at 5 Hz would collect five measurements every second with higher sampling rates generally relating to more accurate measurements (Scott *et al.*, 2016; Theodoropoulos *et al.*, 2020). Modern GPS devices offer frequencies ranging from 1 Hz to 25 Hz, with 10 Hz providing both affordability and high levels of validity, making them the preferred choice for professional sports teams (Scott *et al.*, 2016). However, enhanced validity and reliability can be found in devices measuring at 18 Hz and 20 Hz (Hoppe *et al.*, 2018). The ability of GPS to capture large volumes of external load data such as total running distance, high-speed running (HSR), accelerations and decelerations, coupled with their proven validity and reliability in elite sports environments (Scott *et al.*, 2016), makes GPS the gold standard for measuring the physiological demands of team sports. This data allows coaches and sports scientists to tailor training interventions that mirror the intensity and demands of competitive match play.

For example, GPS has been shown to be effective in determining positional differences in external load outputs for elite level footballers. It has been consistently shown that the volume of HSR efforts varies between playing position (Bloomfield *et al.*, 2007; Di Salvo *et al.*, 2007; Baptista *et al.*, 2018;

De Silva *et al.*, 2018), highlighting clear positional differences in load demands and the need for understanding position specific training and competition demands. GPS has been shown to be a consistent and accurate means of measuring linear and curvilinear distances at high speeds as well as sport specific movements (Varley *et al.*, 2012; Johnstone *et al.*, 2014; Rampinini *et al.*, 2015). However, limitations have been shown measuring movements at high velocities like rapid COD, especially with lower frequency devices (Scott *et al.*, 2016).

Lower-frequency devices (e.g., 1 Hz or 5 Hz) have been shown to struggle when measuring HSR and COD, particularly at high speeds (Portas *et al.*, 2010; Gray *et al.*, 2010). However, these limitations have been largely mitigated with the introduction of higher-frequency models. Johnstone *et al.* (2014) demonstrates 10 Hz devices reliably measure total distance, low-speed running, and HSR with typical errors of measurement (TEM) between 1.3% and 4.8%. Similarly, Rampinini *et al.* (2015) reported comparable accuracy (CV = 4.7%), further confirming the effectiveness of these higher-frequency units. Additionally, Varley *et al.* (2012) showed that 10 Hz devices are reliable for measuring accelerations (CV = 1.9-4.3%), decelerations (CV = 6.0%), and sustained velocity (CV = 2.0-5.3%). Although occasional discrepancies have been reported at the highest speeds, such as percentage errors of 11.5% and 10.5% for VHSR (Johnstone *et al.*, 2014; Rampinini *et al.*, 2015), GPS has been consistently proven to be effective and reliable when measuring physiological load, even at high speeds.

2.2.2 Inertial Measurement Units

Inertial measurement units (IMU) are like GPS units in that they both contain an accelerometer, a 3D gyroscope, and a magnetometer to track human movement. However, the main difference between GPS and IMU is that IMUs do not require satellite connection to capture data, allowing for their use indoors which can expand their use to various indoor sports such as basketball or handball (Luteberget *et al.*, 2018) and other indoor training environments. To allow for almost instantaneous facilitation of data, inertial sensors work at a high sampling frequency often ranging from 200-1000 Hz (Maiwald *et al.*, 2015; Struzik *et al.*, 2015; Hollis *et al.*, 2019). This large sampling frequency is associated with increased accuracy of motion detection and thus increasing the ability to monitor locomotive actions such as sprinting, accelerations and decelerations and COD (Torres-Ronda, Clubb, & Beanland, 2022). It could be theorised that these units would be more reliable at measuring sport specific movements than related technology, such as GPS, which only capture data at a sampling frequency ranging from 1-20 Hz (Malone *et al.*, 2017). Despite this, there is limited research to demonstrate the validity of IMUs in measuring locomotor movements in football.

Prior to their recent use in sports, IMU's have been used within clinical settings to measure movements within general population. Koldenhoven *et al.* (2018) determined wearable sensors to show good to excellent validity when measuring pronation velocity, contact time, and cycle time during treadmill running in recreational runners. Similarly, Horsley *et al.* (2021) demonstrate foot worn IMUs are reliable for measuring gait and stride events ($CV < 7.8\%$) during running movements at various speeds ($2-5 \text{ m/s}^2$) in a healthy population. Zeng *et al.* (2021) also supports these findings suggesting IMUs are valid for measuring running performance at low velocities and linear movements. However, these studies did not include rapid COD or reaching maximum velocities as performed by elite athletes, questioning their validity for use within a sports setting. Alanen *et al.* (2020) reviewed the literature to evaluate the reliability and validity of IMU sensors during COD movement in sports and found IMUs could identify COD events with acceptable validity. However, the results were less valid when measuring movements associated with COD such as movement forces, and accelerations which were typically overestimated by IMUs. The findings reported by Alanen and colleagues (2020), are supported by preceding research which investigated the validity of IMUs during measure human motion (Ghattas & Jarvis, 2021). Ghattas & Jarvis (2021) discussed the validity of IMUs for tracking human motion as their systematic review examined published literature on accelerometers and IMUs to determine their validity and application for tracking human motion. The authors determined that IMU systems showed a high level of agreement for measuring slower and less intense movements. However, when the movement became more demanding, such as a football header or baseball pitch, the validity and reliability of IMUs were reduced significantly as lower Intraclass correlation coefficient values were reported. These authors determined that IMUs could be a valid measuring tool for human movement during simple, single plane tasks, but during more dynamic and intense or sport-specific movements, the validity is much lower. Dasa and colleagues (2022) used various tracking devices, including GPS and PM to monitor energy expenditure in professional female footballers. They used a pre-determined intermittent running course (total distance 2747.5 m) as well as 20 m sprints to measure the devices' ability to record total distance, and distance covered at various speeds from walking to sprinting to calculate caloric energy expenditure. The authors show PM overestimated total distance by an average of 0.7% ($2767 \pm 207 \text{ m}$) compared to the two other GPS devices used, which would agree with Ghattas and Jarvis (2021) who suggest overestimation occurs at faster and more intense movements.

At the commencement of this research, only one study existed measuring the validity and reliability of using foot mounted IMUs to quantify running actions in football. Waldron *et al.* (2021) measured the PM IMU device against three separate GPS devices, alongside measuring interunit reliability during a football specific training protocol involving various forms of acceleration, deceleration, and

COD (Barrett *et al.*, 2013). This test was performed using male professional footballers, and many discrepancies were reported between the IMUs and the GPS devices. Most notably, IMUs consistently recorded significantly greater total distances (25–50 m), greater HSR distance, and greater peak accelerations & decelerations (a total error of up to 3.1 m/s^2) in comparison to all GPS devices. Despite this, no differences were found in measurements of peak velocity and very HSR distance and IMU interunit reliability was shown to be strong for all variables ($p > 0.05$) during a soccer-specific aerobic field test (SAFT90). Ultimately, this research found PM IMUs to be a valid means of measuring football performance, however, this study raises some questions. Firstly, it is unclear what GPS devices were used as the criterion method in this study, as the validity of these devices may influence the results. Additionally, as the authors filtered the raw data of PM from 1000 Hz to 25 Hz it is unknown what the outcome would be if the data was unfiltered. This raises the question of whether this data would be more accurate and lead to less discrepancies in the results due to the significantly higher sampling rate. Additionally, as the researchers used a continuous running drill (SAFT90) to measure these outcomes, it could be suggested that some measures may not be accurately measured due to being performed at a potentially lower intensity, where the validity of PM is unclear. As this current study has progressed, new research has been published investigating the validity and reliability of PM to measure locomotive movements in football. Sandmæl & Dalen (2023) recently compared GPS and PM IMU in measuring total distance, velocity, accelerations, and decelerations during a square running protocol and small-sided games within male semi-professional footballers. They reported GPS and IMU both under-reported mean total distance by 1% and 2% respectively during the square running protocol, with GPS under-reporting by a mean of 14 m and IMU by 25 m. Both devices measured a CV of 1%. IMU also produced lower peak velocity ($\sim 2.7\%$), accelerations in zone 2 and decelerations in zones 2 and 3 during the square running protocol. Conversely, IMU total distance was 4% greater than GPS during small-sided games and had a greater distance in velocity zones 2 and 3, whilst IMU very high-speed running distance was recorded as 18% lower than GPS. Overall, this study demonstrated both devices measure similar total distance during the square running protocol however IMU measures significantly higher total distance during small-sided games. This suggests at higher velocities involving high-speed change of direction PM is less valid. Similarly, the authors reported IMUs produced significantly higher distances at lower velocities than GPS as well as larger numbers of accelerations and decelerations, which is consistent with the findings of Waldron and colleagues (2021). Meanwhile GPS was shown to record significantly higher distance at high velocities, further supporting the suggestion that PM may be less valid when measuring movement at high velocities.

Similarly, Myhill *et al.* (2023) used linear and change of direction running protocols to measure the concurrent validity and between-unit reliability of PM against Qualisys 3D motion capture system as a criterion measure. This study used 10 m flying sprints, a maximal acceleration drill, and 5 x 1 minute 10 seconds repetitions of the SAFT90 running protocol to validate PM. The authors report PM to underestimate peak velocity and acceleration with the largest underestimation found at higher velocities. The researchers suggested PM velocity accuracy during COD activities was dependent on the exercise, with the lowest underestimation found during the SAFT90 and highest error found for the maximal acceleration drill. This may be related to the SAFT90 being performed at a potentially lower velocity due to its continuous nature. As the participants are required to decelerate during the linear sprint, this could suggest they were unable to achieve a high velocity. Whereas, as the maximal acceleration drill is performed with maximal intent, participants may have achieved a greater peak velocity from which PM may be less valid in measuring. This would align with the findings from Sandmæl & Dalen (2023) and previous suggestion that PM is less valid when measuring at high velocity. Myhill and colleagues (2023) reported an increase in measurement error is associated with an increase in velocity, as well as an increase in average difference to the reference system with the authors reporting a small underestimation against the criterion measure (-0.003 to -0.214 m/s⁻¹ respectively). Similarly, during the maximal sprints, PM was shown to underestimate peak velocity especially at higher velocities, however the authors noted the participants were unable to achieve a top speed greater than 8 m/s and thus further research would be required to measure peak velocity. Despite this, Myhill and colleagues (2023) state PM largely underestimates peak velocity at speeds greater than 7 m/s and hypothesise the degree of difference would increase at higher velocities. Despite using a maximal COD drill, Myhill *et al.* (2023) did not appear to discuss PMs ability to measure high speed accelerations or decelerations. However, PM appeared to underestimate maximal acceleration and deceleration with an average difference of -0.214 ± 0.787 m/s and a maximum difference of 3.48 m/s. Further to this, Sandmæl, Tillard & Dalen (2023) investigated the validity and reliability of Polar Team Pro and PM for measuring speed and running distance in both indoor and outdoor conditions. Participants were required to perform straight line and rectangular running at various intensities ranging from 8 to 24 km h⁻¹ while wearing Polar Team Pro and PM sensors. Specifically looking at the results for PM, the authors determined PM to significantly underestimate total distance compared to the actual distance measured for the test, however they still reported good validity as the degree of difference was stated as being less than 5%. When measuring speed, the authors show PM significantly underestimated average speed at all running intensities with the severity of underestimation increasing with increasing speed (2–12%). It is important to mention some key limitations for this research, firstly the small sample size,

as this research had a total of just four participants, this limits the statistical power of the data produced. Further research with a larger participant pool would increase the validity of these results. Secondly, it is unclear what the athletic status of the participants involved within this study was, which could inhibit their ability to perform HSR, acceleration and deceleration activities (Lorenz *et al.*, 2013).

2.2.3 Validity

The validity of a device is measured by its ability to accurately measure what it intends to measure. This is crucial when using GPS or IMUs as accurate reporting is necessary for load management and exercise prescription. The validity of an instrument is often measured as the standard estimate of error (SEE), standard error of measurement (SEM), coefficient of variation (CV), or the percentage of difference of the mean from criterion measures (e.g., Scott *et al.*, 2016). Currently, no single recommendation exists for determining the acceptable error for validity measures (Scott *et al.*, 2016). However, previous research has used adapted recommendations of reliability to apply consistency when measuring validity. For example, Scott *et al.* (2016) rated measures of validity using CV%, as good (<5%), moderate (5–10%), or poor (>10%). This is similar to previous literature from Coutts and Duffield (2010) who also utilised CV% to determine GPS has good to moderate validity when measuring total distance and peak speed (2.3-7.1%), but poor validity at high and very high speeds (11.2-32.4%). Using CV provides a simple and time efficient means of reporting measurement error, however, Scott and colleagues (2016) advise individual interpretation is required when reporting measures of validity due to inconsistent methods used within the literature. Alternatively, Myhill and colleagues (2023) measured validity using root mean square error, 95% limits of agreement (LoA), and mean difference with 95% confidence interval (CI). This shares some similarities with Akenhead *et al.* (2014) who measured 10 Hz GPS validity using SEE with 95% LoA to determine bias between raw and smooth velocity data, meanwhile, Roell *et al.* (2019) used a combination of all these methods to validate wearable sensors. From the current literature, various methods can be used to investigate measurement error and assess validity and no one method is specifically recommended. However, as the cited authors have commonly used CV% to measure both validity and reliability of GPS (Scott *et al.*, 2016), as well as a 95% LoA as a measure of validity for GPS and IMUs, this could be considered an acceptable method for measuring PM validity.

2.3 Football Performance Tests

Physical performance assessment is an integral component of elite football, where teams aim to develop and maintain performance while mitigating injury risk. Focus is generally fixed on speed,

muscular strength, change of direction, and aerobic capacity, which offer an opportunity to evaluate a player's physical qualities, guide talent identification, player selection and programming (Beere & Jeffreys, 2021).

Test selection should be based on assessment of the specific demands of the sport, then matching these demands with appropriate tests (Cone, 2012). Validity and reliability of the selected tests needs to be considered, how accurately does the test measure what it is intended to measure, and what is the reproducibility of the test (Cone, 2012). As football is an intermittent endurance sport with frequent bouts of sprinting, changes in intensity, and frequent changes of direction, selected tests should measure maximal sprint speed, acceleration and deceleration capabilities, ability to effectively change direction, and aerobic capacity (Beere & Jeffreys, 2021). These areas will provide valuable information of a player's physical qualities, strengths and weaknesses, and readiness to perform.

2.3.1 Football specific simulation test

Football-specific simulation tests can be used to evaluate performance metrics that replicate the physical demands of match play. The SAFT90, a high-intensity, football-specific simulation course, has been used to assess player loads during a game-like scenario (Barrett *et al.*, 2013). This test consists of multidirectional movements with frequent changes in intensity over two 45-minute halves, separated by a 15-minute interval, guided by audio instructions. It involves various locomotion types like walking, jogging, striding, and sprinting, along a 20-meter course, covering up to 10.78km with frequent COD, totalling 484 meters (Barrett *et al.*, 2013).

Despite its ability to mimic the loads experienced during competitive match-play, the SAFT90's duration (90 minutes) may present practical limitations, particularly in elite football settings, where time constraints exist. Due to this, shorter alternatives such as the SAFT5 (5 minutes) have emerged, offering a more time-efficient test while still maintaining the essential elements of player load. Bossuyt *et al.* (2016) validated the SAFT5 by demonstrating that it elicited heart rates consistent with those observed in female match play (Andersson *et al.*, 2010; Krstrup *et al.*, 2010), making it an appropriate alternative for monitoring aerobic performance in footballers. Similarly, Myhill *et al.* (2023) adapted the SAFT90 protocol into shorter 1-minute segments, but the validity of this method for accurately replicating match conditions is still unclear. The validity and reliability of shortened versions of the SAFT90, remain less well-researched, and more data is needed to evaluate how closely they replicate match-play demands in elite settings.

2.3.2 Linear Speed

Linear sprinting ability is a critical attribute for success in football (Little & Williams, 2005), particularly given that sprint actions often determine match-defining moments such as breaking defensive lines or covering large distances quickly. Linear speed testing typically focuses on two phases: acceleration (first 5-10 m) and maximal sprint speed (20-40 m) (Haddad *et al.*, 2015). In football, where players cover distances of 5 to 40 m during sprint bouts, assessing speed at these distances provides a specific and relevant measure of in-game performance (Altmann *et al.*, 2019).

Dual-beam timing gates are considered a gold standard in speed testing for football and are used to increase the accuracy and reliability of sprint tests, which are crucial in obtaining valid measures of acceleration and top speed (Haugen *et al.*, 2014). Dual-beam timing gates have been shown to be more accurate and reliable than single-beam systems for speed testing in sports, including sprinting and field sports like football (Haugen *et al.*, 2014). Haugen and colleagues (2014) found dual-beam systems provide a lower SEM, around 0.02 seconds, with a CV ranging from 1% to 2%, depending on the distance tested (e.g., 0-20 m or 20-40 m). The main advantage of dual-beam gates is their ability to reduce measurement errors caused by limb movement (such as arms or legs prematurely breaking a single beam).

The literature highlights variability in linear sprint performance (see *Table 2*), particularly in female football, depending on league and competition level. For instance, sprint times over 5 m in elite female football range from 1.00 to 1.15 seconds, with the highest performances reported in the English Women's Super League (Turner, 2016). This variation emphasises the need for more research to standardize normative data across different levels of competition. Additionally, research comparing 5 m sprint performances across different leagues such as Polish Women's National League (Stepinski *et al.*, 2020) and the Portuguese 1st Division (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021) has shown variable results, underscoring the importance of considering the level of competition and the player's physical conditioning.

Similarly, literature reports variable results in sprint times over 10 m in elite female football ranging from 1.81 to 1.90 seconds (Turner, 2016; Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021). As well as 30 m sprint times ranging from 4.489 to 4.75 seconds (Stepinski *et al.*, 2020; Gonçalves *et al.*, 2021). The differences in sprint performance reported within the current literature (see *Table 2*) highlights the difficulty of providing an evidence-based approach to female football testing, demonstrating the requirement for further research.

Notably, Cardoso de Araújo *et al.* (2020) found that females produced significantly lower results for all linear and non-linear speed tests compared to their male counterparts. Looking specifically at linear speed, the results found females to be 8.8%, 10.5%, 11.8%, and 13.6% lower than males for the 5 m, 10 m, 20 m, and 30 m linear sprints respectively. The most comparable results were seen in the 5 m and 10 m sprint tests. This may be a result of almost 95% of sprint distance reported in elite female football ranging between 0-10 m (Datson *et al.*, 2017), emphasising the importance of acceleration and explosiveness in the female game.

2.3.3 Agility and Change of Direction

Agility, defined as the ability to rapidly change velocity or direction in response to a stimulus (Sheppard & Young, 2005), is critical in football, where players must frequently adjust to changes in ball possession or the positioning of opponents (Sporis *et al.*, 2010). Mara *et al.* (2017) demonstrates the high volume of accelerations and decelerations in female soccer, highlighting the importance of player's efficiency in changing direction. Various tests have been utilised within recent literature to assess agility and COD in football, the Illinois agility test and T-Test agility are frequently used in elite sport and have a typical test length of between 14-18 seconds and 10-12 seconds, respectively (Ryan *et al.*, 2021).

The 505 COD test is widely used to measure COD ability, which involves sprinting 5 m, performing a 180-degree COD, and sprinting back 5 m (Ryan *et al.*, 2021). This test may be more suitable to assess COD ability in football as it more closely mimics the demands of football where high intensity efforts and repeated sprint bouts have an average duration of 4 seconds (Di Mascio *et al.*, 2013; Mara *et al.*, 2017). This test, which can be performed using dual-beam timing gates for increased accuracy, is highly relevant to football, where accelerations and decelerations are common (Mara *et al.*, 2017). Studies have shown (see *Table 1*) that the 505 COD test provides reliable results (CV = 1.9–2.4%) and effectively measures COD performance (Barber *et al.*, 2016; Stewart *et al.*, 2014). In elite female footballers, Turner (2016) reported normative data for the 505 COD test, with times under 2.54 seconds classified as 'good.'

As female football continues to evolve, more research is needed to validate the use of different agility tests within this context. Despite being validated in male players, the accuracy of COD tests in female football remains underexplored, highlighting a need for further investigation.

2.3.4 Aerobic Performance

Endurance is a critical component of football performance, given the need to sustain high-intensity performance throughout the 90 minutes of a match. Elite footballers often cover more than 10 km per game (Bangsbo *et al.* 2006), requiring both aerobic endurance and anaerobic capacity for performing repeated high-intensity actions, such as sprints, accelerations, and recovery runs.

The 1 km time trial (1 km TT) is a test used to assess players' aerobic capacity and sustained running ability. This test is an alternative to more traditional endurance tests like the YoYo Intermittent Recovery Test (YoYoIR1), which is a gold standard test for intermittent sports like football (Bangsbo *et al.*, 2008). The 1 km TT requires Players to run ten 100 m lengths as fast as possible, providing a measure of their aerobic capacity allowing coaches to measure maximal aerobic speed (Clancy *et al.*, 2020).

The validity and reliability of the 1 km TT is less frequently studied than other tests, however, recent literature highlights its validity for use in elite football. Clancy *et al.*, (2020) found the 1 km TT to have a linear relationship with the YoYoIR1 as well as strong between session reliability (CV=1.06%). The authors emphasise this tests ease of administration and thus its ability to allow for more frequent testing during the competitive season compared to other tests such as the YoYoIR1.

Despite the practicality of the 1 km TT, its continuous nature may not capture the intermittent endurance demands of football as accurately as other tests like the YoYoIR1. Additionally, Clancy and colleagues also suggest the 1 km TT may overestimate maximal aerobic speed in comparison to longer time trials, therefore caution should be taken during this measurement.

2.3.5 Summary

From the current literature, knowledge gaps exist relating to the validity of foot based IMU's to measure elite football performance, coupled with a growing demand for research relating to elite female football. Although recent literature has investigated the validity of PM for use within football (Waldron *et al.*, 2021), due to conflicting results within this literature, further research is required. Furthermore, due to limitations that exist in relation to the protocols used during previous validation research, there is a need for further data using a greater selection of performance tests which can be measured against the results of the current literature. Additionally, as current literature has mainly utilised male players as their participants (Randell *et al.*, 2021), a literature gap exists relating to the performance requirements of female football players, and if this would have an influence on the results. This research will therefore aim to determine the validity of the PM IMU to report key physical performance metrics in elite female football. This study will use a combination of

performance tests (20 m sprint, 5 m acceleration, 505 left & right, 1 km TT) which have been demonstrated to be valid measures of football performance (Little & Williams, 2005; Bloomfeild *et al.*, 2007; Altmann *et al.*, 2019; Clancy *et al.*, 2020). This research investigates the validity of PM compared to a validated GPS device (Catapult Playertek). Due to the higher sampling frequency of PM, it would be hypothesised that PM would provide increased accuracy when measuring movements at a higher velocity where GPS has been reported to be limited. However, discrepancies reported within current PM literature (Waldron *et al.* 2021; Myhill *et al.* 2023; Sandmæl & Dalen, 2023) do not support this and would suggest further investigation is required.

Table 2. Normative Data for Performance Tests in Football

Assessment	Author/Year	Participants	Devices	Methods	Results
5 m Sprint	Cardoso de Araújo <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Elite female footballers	Double-light barriers (TDS, Werthner Sport Consulting, Linz, Austria)	Measured during 30 m maximal sprint	1.19 ± 0.08 (s)
	Stepinski <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Elite female footballers	Optical measurement system (Microgate Witty, Bolzano, Italy)	Measured during 30 m maximal sprint	1.121 ± 0.079 (s)
	Turner (2016)	Elite Female footballers (WSL)	Single-beam timing gates (Brower SpeedTrap 2 Wireless Timing System)	Measured during 20 m maximal sprint	1.05 to 1.07 (s)
20 m Sprint	Cardoso de Araújo <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Elite female footballers	Double-light barriers (TDS, Werthner Sport Consulting, Linz, Austria)	Measured during 30 m maximal sprint	3.42 ± 0.13 (s)
	Gabbett <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Elite female Soccer Academy	Dual-beam timing gates (Swift performance)	Measured during 20 m maximal sprint	3.20 to 3.30 (s)
	Turner (2016)	Elite Female footballers (WSL)	Single-beam timing gates (Brower SpeedTrap 2 Wireless Timing System)	Measured during 20 m maximal sprint	3.29 to 3.35 (s)
505 COD	Turner (2016)	Elite Female footballers (WSL)	Single-beam timing gates (Brower SpeedTrap 2 Wireless Timing System)	5 m sprint + 180° + 5 m sprint	2.67 to 2.70 (s)
1km TT	Clancy <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Elite male footballers	N/A	10 x 100 m shuttle runs	CV=1.06%
SAFT90	Barret <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Elite youth male footballers	Catapult GPS	Multidirectional movement course 2 x 45min halves.	10.78 km total distance.
	Bossuyt <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Active females	Heart rate monitor (Polar heart rate system, Electro, Finland)	Shortened 5min version of SAFT90	89 ± 4% HRmax

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Participants

Fourteen senior elite female football players (age: 22.8 ± 4.0 years; body mass: 60.1 ± 3.5 kg; height: 167.8 ± 5.4 cm) from a Scottish Women's Premier League team were recruited through convenience sampling to take part in this validation research study. Two players were excluded from this study, both were goalkeepers, as only data from outfield players was used for analysis, and one player was unable to complete all test parameters. Therefore, peak velocity and 1 km TT contains data from twelve players, meanwhile, only data from eleven players was used in final analysis for peak acceleration and deceleration. Testing took place during the in-season period and all players were registered to the same club, were participating members of the club's senior team, and were 18 years old and over. Prior to commencing data collection, a medical questionnaire (Appendix 1), and a written consent form (Appendix 2) was obtained from all participants, and ethical approval for this research was granted by the School Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at University of the West of Scotland (approval number: 15468). Participant's personal data such as name and date of birth were removed and replaced with a participant number (e.g., athlete 1, athlete 2) to ensure no participants personal data could be identified.

3.2 Equipment

Participant's took part in various physical performance tests while wearing PlayerMaker (PlayerMaker, PlayerMaker LTD, London) devices on the lateral surface of the foot via a purpose-made silicone strap (Waldron *et al.*, 2021), while simultaneously wearing a GPS (Playertek, Catapult Sports, Melbourne) unit attached via a fitted neoprene vest sitting parallel between the scapulae (McLellan *et al.*, 2011). The PlayerMaker units collected data at a frequency rate of 1000 Hz, Waldron *et al.* (2021) filtered data post-hoc to sample at 25 Hz using a zero-lag Butterworth filter however the data was kept at 1000 Hz for this research. Meanwhile, the GPS device captured data at a rate of 10 Hz which has been shown to be both valid and reliable at capturing running velocities at various intensities and distances (Johnston *et al.*, 2014; Rampinini *et al.*, 2015; Varley *et al.*, 2012; Scott *et al.*, 2016; Battaler-Cervero *et al.*, 2019). In accordance with the timings reported by Waldron *et al.* (2021), the GPS units were turned on 20 minutes prior to testing, to allow maximum sync to the satellite servers while the PM devices were turned on 10 minutes prior to the performance as per Waldron *et al.* (2021).

Dual beam timing gates were used to measure sprint times (Brower TCI system, United States) and placed 20 m apart for the 20 m sprint and 5 m apart for the 5 m and 505 tests. These gates were set

at a height of 84 cm to allow the infra-red beam between gates to be broken at hip height (Yeadon *et al.*, 1999; Altmann *et al.*, 2017).

3.3 Protocol

The physical performance tests used within this study include 20 m linear sprint, 5 m linear sprint, 505 left and right, and 1 km time trial. Prior to commencing the testing session, participants performed a 10 to 15-minute warm-up following the RAMP protocol – Raise, Activate, Motivate, Potentiate (Jeffreys, 2007). This consisted of two laps of an 11-a-side football pitch, and dynamic stretches such as hip opening and closing, straight leg kicks, quad stretch, and ground sweeps. This was followed by muscle activation exercises such as lunges, toe walks, pogos, before moving onto more movement specific preparation including A-skips, B-skips, bounds, and various accelerations. The test protocol was explained to the participants, with the tests performed in the following order: 20 m, 5 m, 505 Left, 505 Right, 1 km TT. These tests were performed in dry, low wind conditions and there were no surrounding buildings which could interfere with the signal of the GPS.

The participants were first instructed to perform two maximal effort 20 m sprint attempts, followed separately by two maximal 5 m sprint attempts and instructed to keep accelerating until they had passed through the last pair of timing gates (20 m line and 5 m line, respectively). To allow full recovery, subjects were given a minimum of 120 seconds between 20 m attempts and 30 seconds between 5 m attempts. The start line was positioned 1 m behind the first timing gate (0 m line) to avoid a false trigger of the beam. Similarly, participants were then instructed to perform four maximal effort 505 COD attempts (2 left, 2 right) with 120 seconds given between efforts for full recovery. As instructed previously, participants were encouraged to keep accelerating beyond the timing gates and started 1 m behind the starting line to prevent a false trigger of the beam.

Following the completion of all sprint and COD tests, participants were then instructed to perform one maximal effort 1 km TT. Each subject completed 10x100 m runs performed on a 4G football pitch with times recorded via stopwatch.

3.4 Peak Velocity

Peak velocity was measured using a 20 m linear sprint test. This test was selected as 20 m sprints are commonly observed during football matches (Chelly *et al.*, 2010; Bangsbo, 1991) and have been used to reliably measure maximal speed and acceleration in footballers within sports literature (Little & Williams, 2005; Altmann *et al.*, 2019). Each participant performed three maximal efforts with a minimum of 120 seconds of recovery provided between efforts. The rest time between sprints was selected as it has been recommended athletes require 60 seconds rest for every 10 m covered when performing maximal sprint bouts (Haugen *et al.*, 2019). Velocity thresholds used to

define HSR, and sprinting were measured at 15-16 km/h and 20 km/h, respectively (Bradley & Vescovi, 2014). These values were selected as HSR and sprinting values are often under reported in females as per Bradley & Vescovi (2014), as females have been demonstrated to have lower speed and power outputs than males (Hallom and Amorim, 2022).

3.5 Peak Acceleration

Peak acceleration was measured during a 5 m sprint test. This test was selected as literature demonstrates 95% of all sprints measured in elite female football are between 0-10 m (Datson *et al.*, 2017) with 5 m sprints most observed during football matches (Chelly *et al.*, 2010; Bangsbo, 1991). Each participant performed three maximal efforts with a minimum of 30 seconds of recovery provided between efforts, based on the previous recommendations from Haugen *et al.* (2019).

3.6 Change of Direction

The 505 COD test was chosen due to the volume of accelerations, decelerations, and changes of direction reported within football literature (Bloomfield *et al.*, 2007). Participants were instructed to accelerate 5 m, turn 180° on a pre-determined leg, and accelerate back 5 m (Sayers, 2015) ensuring not to decelerate before crossing the finish line. Each participant performed two attempts turning on the left leg and then two attempts on the right, with a minimum of 120 seconds rest between attempts. This minimum rest time was provided due to the greater physical demand of this test; however, previous literature has provided a maximum recovery time of 180 seconds (Sayers, 2015). Participants were instructed to perform each attempt maximally, and any attempt where the participant did not touch the turn line, they were asked to rest 120 seconds and repeat their attempt. PM records accelerations and decelerations as speed > -2 m/s² for at least 0.5 seconds. Therefore, Catapult GPS devices were also set to measure accelerations and decelerations at the same speed threshold.

3.7 Time Trial

The 1 km TT was selected to allow for a comparison of total distance and average acceleration and velocity between PM IMU and the Playertek GPS. The total length of the football pitch used during testing was 100 m as measured using measuring tape, therefore participants performed 10 x 100 m shuttle lengths to achieve the required 1000 m distance (Clancy *et al.*, 2020). To ensure the participant's achieved the required distance, each participant was instructed to touch the white line and/or marker with their foot as they changed direction. Clancy and colleagues (2020) placed poles 100 m apart and instructed participants to touch the pole, whereas, in this study, two coaches were placed at either end of the pitch to monitor adherence, and times were recorded via stopwatch. As the total distance of this test was measured as 1000 m, the purpose of this protocol was to assess how accurately PM can measure total distance when the actual distance is known.

3.8 Data Handling

Start and end times were recorded for each performance test and all participants were required to be stationary up to 30 seconds before performing each attempt (Beato *et al.*, 2018). This allowed for a clear starting point to be determined for each participant, as a rapid increase in velocity can be identified. All test attempts were cut and formatted into a 'drill' according to the recorded test times for each participant on both respective device's software. Catapult Playertek's in-built speed graph allowed for exact start and end times to be set for each test attempt, with data then exported to CSV file for analysis. A limitation was found with the PM software when defining the exact starting point of a test. This was affected by the ability of the software's speed graph to allow free selection of a starting time and caused some drills to be created with ± 0.2 second excess. To combat this, raw CSV files were exported to Microsoft Excel for analysis. Speed graphs were created and used to determine peak velocity during 20 m linear sprint, peak acceleration during 5 m linear sprint, peak acceleration, and deceleration during both 505 right and left tests, and total distance during 1 km TT. Peak velocity, acceleration, and deceleration were measured as the highest velocity value during the 20 m sprint, 5 m acceleration, and 505 left and right tests, and derived directly from the devices software without requiring additional calculation for peak values. Only the best attempt for each participant was used within the analysis, and data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

3.9 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using Jamovi analysis software (Jamovi 1.6.15). Shapiro-Wilk's test was used to test the normal distribution of the data and paired sample T-Tests were used to test for significant differences in performance metrics recorded between GPS and PM devices. Additionally, the coefficient of variation (CV%) was used to measure the validity of PM by measuring the relative variation of the data and determined as good (<5%), moderate (5–10%), or poor (>10%) (Scott *et al.*, 2016). Intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) \pm 95% confidence intervals (CI) were also determined and reported as <0.5 poor, 0.5–0.75 moderate, 0.75–0.9 good and >0.9 excellent (Koo and Li, 2016). ICCs (3,1) were selected as the "3" refers subjects is a random effect and the trials is a fixed effect, while the "1" refers to the reliability of single repeated measurements as stated by Shrout and Fleiss (1979). Measurement error was assessed using SEM and SEE and Bland & Altman's analysis was used to identify systematic bias between measurement devices to determine any under/overestimation of values reported from the PM unit. Smallest worthwhile change (SWC) was calculated as 0.2 multiplied by the between-subject standard deviation for each performance test (Sullivan and Feinn, 2012), based on Cohen's effect size principle, where 0.2 represents a small, but not trivial, effect size.

Chapter 4: Results

4.1 20 m Sprint Peak Velocity

The 20 m sprint peak velocity was significantly lower for PM (6.79 ± 0.36 m/s) compared with GPS (7.27 ± 0.29 m/s); $t(11) = 8.18$, mean difference [95% CI] = -0.48 m/s [-0.66 m/s, -0.38 m/s], $p < 0.001$ (Figure 1), effect size = 2.36.

Figure 1. Mean 20 m sprint peak velocity measured by PlayerMaker (PM) and Global Positioning System (GPS) (* denotes significant difference $P < 0.001$)

There was a good relationship between PM and GPS [ICC 0.81, 95% CI 0.46 – 0.94] (Figure 2). The CV was 2.21% and SEM and SEE were 0.16 m/s and 0.25 m/s respectively. PM appeared to underestimate peak velocity in comparison to GPS, showing significant consistent bias with a large scatter and wide LoA, mean difference [95% CI] = -0.48 m/s [-0.66 m/s, -0.38 m/s] (Lower LoA [95% CI] -0.95 [-1.20 , -0.70], Upper LoA [95% CI] -0.09 [-0.33 , 0.16]). Smallest worthwhile change is measured as a difference ≥ 0.06 m/s.

Figure 2. Bland-Altman plot 20 m sprint peak velocity measured by PM & GPS

4.2 5 m Peak Acceleration

The 5 m peak acceleration was significantly lower for PM ($3.75 \pm 0.53 \text{ m/s}^2$) compared with GPS ($5.07 \pm 0.33 \text{ m/s}^2$); $t(11) = 7.60$, mean difference [95% CI] = -1.32 m/s^2 [-1.72, -0.94], $p < 0.001$ (Figure 3), effect size = -2.29.

Figure 3. Mean 5m peak acceleration measured by PM & GPS (* denotes significant difference $P < 0.001$)

There was a poor relationship between PM and GPS (ICC 0.14, 95% CI -0.38 – 0.60). The CV was 9.29% and SEM and SEE were 0.41 m/s^2 and 0.39 m/s^2 respectively. PM appeared to underestimate peak acceleration, showing significant consistent bias with a large scatter and wide LoA, mean difference [95% CI] = -1.32 m/s^2 [-1.72 m/s^2 , -0.94 m/s^2] (Lower LoA [95% CI] -2.46 [-3.20 , -1.78], Upper LoA [95% CI] -0.19 [-0.88 , 0.50]), see Figure 4. Smallest worthwhile change is measured as a difference $\geq 0.06 \text{ m/s}^2$.

Figure 4. Bland-Altman plot 5m peak acceleration measured by PM & GPS

4.3 505 Left Peak Acceleration

The 505 Left peak acceleration was significantly lower for PM ($3.88 \pm 0.55 \text{ m/s}^2$) compared with GPS ($5.13 \pm 0.64 \text{ m/s}^2$); $t(11) = 4.33$, mean difference [95% CI] = -1.25 m/s^2 [-1.90, -0.61], $p < 0.01$ (see Figure 5), effect size = -1.31.

Figure 5. Mean 505 Left peak acceleration measured by PM & GPS (* denotes significant difference $P < 0.01$)

There was a poor relationship between PM and GPS (ICC -0.31, 95% CI -0.70 – 0.22) (Figure 6). The CV was 13.28% and SEM and SEE were 0.60 m/s^2 and 0.00 m/s^2 respectively. PM appeared to underestimate peak acceleration, showing significant consistent bias with a large scatter and wide LoA, mean difference [95% CI] = -1.25 m/s^2 [-1.90 m/s^2 , -0.61 m/s^2] (Upper LoA [95% CI] 3.13 [-4.27, -2.00], Lower LoA [95% CI] -0.63 [-0.51 - 1.76]). Smallest worthwhile change is measured as a difference $\geq 0.07 \text{ m/s}^2$.

Figure 6. Bland-Altman plot 505 Left peak acceleration as measured by PM & GPS

4.4 505 Left Peak Deceleration

The 505 Left peak deceleration was significantly lower for PM ($2.88 \pm 0.46 \text{ m/s}^2$) compared with GPS ($5.88 \pm 0.86 \text{ m/s}^2$); $t(11) = 11.50$, mean difference [95% CI] = -3.00 m/s^2 [-3.58, -2.42], $p < 0.001$ (Figure 7), effect size = -3.47.

Figure 7. Mean 505 Left peak deceleration measured by PM & GPS (* denotes significant difference $P < 0.001$)

There was a poor relationship between PM and GPS (ICC 0.24, 95% CI -0.29 – 0.66) (Figure 8). The CV was 13.93% and SEM and SEE were 0.61 m/s^2 and 1.00 m/s^2 respectively. PM appeared to underestimate deceleration, showing significant consistent bias with a large scatter and wide LoA, mean difference [95% CI] = -3.00 m/s^2 [-3.58 m/s^2 , -2.42 m/s^2] (Lower LoA [95% CI] -4.69 [-5.71 , -3.66], Upper LoA [95% CI] -1.30 [-2.33 , -0.28]), smallest worthwhile change is measured as a difference $\geq 0.10 \text{ m/s}^2$.

Figure 8. Bland-Altman plot 505 Left peak deceleration as measured by PM & GPS

4.5 505 Right Peak Acceleration

The 505 Right peak acceleration was significantly lower for PM ($3.81 \pm 0.45 \text{ m/s}^2$) compared with GPS ($4.73 \pm 0.54 \text{ m/s}^2$); $t(11) = 4.60$, mean difference [95% CI] = -0.92 m/s^2 [-1.37, -0.48], $p < 0.001$ (Figure 9), effect size = -1.39.

Figure 9. Mean 505 Right peak acceleration measured by GPS & PM (* denotes significant difference $P < 0.001$)

There was a poor relationship between PM and GPS (ICC 0.14, 95% CI -0.39 – 0.59) (Figure 10). The CV was 11.01% and SEM and SEE were 0.47 m/s^2 and 0.32 m/s^2 respectively. PM appeared to underestimate acceleration, showing significant consistent bias with a large scatter and wide LoA, mean difference [95% CI] = -0.92 m/s^2 [0.48 m/s^2 , 1.37 m/s^2] (Lower LoA [95% CI] -2.23 [-3.01 , -1.44], Upper LoA [95% CI] -0.38 [-0.40 , 1.17]). Smallest worthwhile change is measured as a difference $\geq 0.07 \text{ m/s}^2$.

Figure 10. Bland-Altman plot 505 Right peak acceleration measured by PM & GPS

4.6 505 Right Peak Deceleration

The 505 Right peak deceleration was significantly lower for PM ($3.14 \pm 0.47 \text{ m/s}^2$) compared with GPS ($5.19 \pm 0.67 \text{ m/s}^2$); $t(11) = 8.47$, mean difference [95% CI] = -2.05 m/s^2 [-2.60, -1.52], $p < 0.001$ (Figure 11), effect size = -2.55.

Figure 11. Mean 505 Right peak deceleration measured by PM & GPS (* denotes significant difference $P < 0.001$)

There was a poor relationship between PM and GPS (ICC 0.02, 95% CI -0.48 – 0.52) (Figure 12). The CV was 13.69% and SEM and SEE were 0.57 m/s^2 and 0.25 m/s^2 respectively. PM appeared to underestimate deceleration, showing significant consistent bias with a large scatter and wide LoA, mean difference [95% CI] = -2.05 m/s^2 [-2.60 m/s^2 , -1.52 m/s^2] (Lower LoA [95% CI] -3.64 [-4.60, -2.68], Upper LoA [95% CI] -0.48 [-1.43, 0.48]). Smallest worthwhile change is measured as a difference $\geq 0.08 \text{ m/s}^2$.

Figure 12. Bland-Altman plot 505 Right peak deceleration as measured by PM & GPS

4.7 1 km Total Distance

Total distance was significantly lower for PM (965 ± 17.6 m) compared with GPS (988 ± 11.3 m); $t(11) = 4.36$, mean difference [95% CI] = -23 m [-35.50 , -11.70], $p < 0.01$ (Figure 13), effect size = -1.26 .

Figure 13. Mean total distance measured by PM & GPS (* denotes significant difference $P < 0.01$)

There was a poor relationship between PM and GPS (ICC 0.21, 95% CI $-0.32 - 0.64$) (Figure 14). The CV was 1.36% and SEM and SEE were 13.24 m and 10.95 m respectively. PM appeared to underestimate total distance, showing significant consistent bias with a large scatter and very wide LoA, mean difference [95% CI] = -23 m [-35.50 m, -11.70 m] (Lower LoA [95% CI] -60.3 [-81.20 , -39.3], Upper LoA [95% CI] 13.1 [-7.82 , 34.00]). Smallest worthwhile change is measured as a difference ≥ 2.00 m.

Figure 14. Bland-Altman plot Total Distance as measured by PM & GPS

Chapter 5: Discussion

The aim of this research was to determine the concurrent validity of the PM IMU to measure key physical performance metrics in elite female football. This study measured the ability of PM to produce peak velocity, peak acceleration, peak deceleration, and total distance against a valid Catapult GPS device. The results from this study found PM to significantly underestimate all parameters in comparison to Catapult GPS with a poor to good relationship shown between devices. Although significance was determined between measures, good agreement was found for PM when measuring peak velocity and total distance, however poor to moderate agreement was found for peak acceleration and poor agreement for peak deceleration. It was hypothesised that PM would show to be a valid means of measuring physical performance metrics in football, especially high velocity movements, due to its higher sampling frequency than GPS. However, the findings from this research were unable to determine its validity and highlights the demand for further investigation.

5.1 Peak Velocity

The results for this present study demonstrated that peak velocity during the 20 m sprint was 6.6% lower using the PM compared with the GPS. This result is consistent with the findings of Sandmæl and Dalen (2023), who reported that PM underestimated peak velocity compared to GPS, though only by 2.7%. The variation in the magnitude of underestimation between studies may be attributed to differences in testing protocols. Sandmæl and Dalen (2023) implemented a continuous square running protocol, which may have resulted in peak velocity being measured at a lower threshold than what is typically observed during a maximal sprint. According to Myhill *et al.* (2023), velocities exceeding 7 m/s are more prone to underestimation when using PM compared to GPS. Since Sandmæl and Dalen did not reach this velocity threshold, they likely avoided this underestimation, whereas, in this current study the mean peak velocity during the 20 m sprint was greater than 7 m/s. This could suggest that at higher velocities, the degree of underestimation by PM is greater, which is supported by Sandmæl, Tillard & Dalen (2023) who found PM to significantly underestimate speed at all intensities from walking to sprinting with the magnitude of underestimation increasing at higher velocity (2-12%). However, although Myhill *et al.* (2023) used similar testing protocols to this present study and that of Waldron *et al.* (2021), these authors used a 3D motion capture system which is not the gold-standard method of measuring peak velocity. Therefore, there needs to be further study into the differences in peak velocity at various speeds with PM and GPS as opposed to 3D motion capture as direct comparisons cannot be made.

Whilst there is support from other studies in relation to our findings, it is in contrast to findings by Waldron *et al.* (2021) who stated no differences in peak velocity between PM and GPS. These

differences between the present study and that of Waldron *et al.* (2021) may be again related to the different testing protocols used. The validity of the SAFT90 to measure peak velocity is unclear as the course has a continuous nature may influence the intensity from which the protocol would be performed. This present study used a maximal 20 m sprint test which is commonly used to measure linear speed in footballers (Little & Williams, 2005; Altmann *et al.*, 2019), whereas Waldron and colleagues measured peak velocity as the fastest 0.3 second period during the SAFT90 (Barret *et al.*, 2013). During the SAFT90, the participants also performed a 20 m linear sprint, however this was performed during a continuous running drill involving change of direction which will inhibit the participants ability to achieve top speed along with the need to turn into an acceleration and decelerate before reaching the full 20 m. This would suggest peak velocity was measured at a lower magnitude; however, this cannot be confirmed. If participants were performing the linear sprint portion of the SAFT90 at a lower velocity, PM would show greater validity than if participants were reaching near top speed as suggested by Myhill *et al.* (2023) and Sandmæl, Tillard & Dalen (2023). There are clear methodological differences in measures between peak velocity measures between this research and that of Waldon and colleagues which calls into question the methods used to measure peak velocity by Waldron *et al.*, (2021) and hence the validity of PM to measure peak velocity.

While PM has been demonstrated to underestimate peak velocity, the statistical analysis performed in this study shows PM to have good agreement, indicating that the underestimation by PM is unlikely to be of concern ($SWC \geq 0.06$ m/s). Similar findings have been reported by other authors (Myhill *et al.*, 2023; Sandmæl & Dalen, 2023; Sandmæl, Tillard & Dalen, 2023), who observed comparable mean differences. Although PM may underestimate peak velocity, and in some cases overestimate it, as noted by Waldron *et al.* (2021), the validity of PM for measuring peak velocity remains inconclusive, highlighting the need for further research.

The variation reported between devices measuring peak velocity can likely be attributed to technological differences between PM and GPS, as well as different testing protocols utilised within the existing literature (Torres-Ronda *et al.*, 2022). As a valid 10 Hz GPS (Scott *et al.*, 2016) was used as the criterion method against PM (measuring at 1000 Hz), future investigations may wish to use a GPS device with a higher sampling frequency (15-25 Hz), to reduce any measurement error at high velocities. Additionally, further investigations may benefit from measuring PM and GPS during a graded exercise test or similar to compare both devices at different velocities to determine where the differences occur and when does the underestimation become significant. Due to the findings of this study conflicting previous literature, PM validity cannot be concluded for measuring peak velocity in football, suggesting further investigation is required.

5.2 Peak Acceleration

PM significantly underestimated peak acceleration compared with GPS during 5 m acceleration and during 505 left and right tests. Results suggested that there was moderate to poor validity in these performance metrics when measured by PM. For the 5 m acceleration, PM underestimates peak acceleration with an average difference of 26.04% which suggests PM has a moderate validity with a corresponding CV of 9.29%. Additionally, mean difference ranged from 21.55% to 27.75% during both 505 left and right tests with poor validity reported (CV = 13.28% and 11.01% respectively). This suggests PM may be less valid for measuring peak acceleration. These findings are akin to those reported by Myhill *et al.* (2022) who show PM to underestimate peak acceleration and reported a mean difference of $-0.214 \pm 0.787 \text{ m/s}^2$ and a maximal difference of 3.48 m/s^2 between PM and GPS systems. An increase in velocity performed during the test resulted in an increase in underestimation from PM, while also suggesting results are exercise dependent as underestimation was greater during the SAFT90 than during the maximal acceleration drill, which would have been performed at a higher velocity. This suggestion is supported by Alanen *et al.* (2020) who found IMUs to be less reliable at measuring high velocity accelerations during COD movements, although the authors determined this due to be an overestimation by the IMU sensor rather than an underestimation. Additionally, Ghattas & Jarvis (2021) also determined IMUs to be less accurate during dynamic high velocity movements, which would suggest that at high velocities PMs validity for measuring peak acceleration is reduced.

Despite this, the findings reported within this present study are conflicting with those reported by Waldron *et al.* (2021) and Alanen *et al.* (2021) who both found PM to overestimate peak acceleration. Waldron and colleagues (2021) found IMUs validity ranged from poor to acceptable, meanwhile Alanen and colleagues (2021) suggests IMUs to have acceptable validity when measuring COD events but determined IMUs to overestimate variables relating to COD performance such as accelerations and decelerations. These results are supported by findings from Horsely *et al.* (2021) and Zeng *et al.* (2021) who found foot worn IMU's to have moderate validity for measuring stride events in a general population. The difference in results reported between studies may be affected by the difference in tracking devices used. This present study along with Waldron *et al.* (2021) investigated PM validity against GPS, whereas others compared IMUs against various other motion trackers such as force plates, high-speed cameras, and 3-D motion capture systems (Alanen *et al.*, 2021; Myhill *et al.*, 2022), highlighting a lack of consistency in the literature for means of IMU validation. Regardless, as PM has been reported to both overestimate and underestimate peak acceleration against the combination of various tracking devices used, further research is required.

GPS has been shown to be valid when measuring acceleration during linear and change of direction movements (Varley *et al.*, 2012; Scott *et al.*, 2016). However, published literature has suggested GPS validity can be reduced during rapid changes of direction (Rawstorn *et al.*, 2014). Rawstorn and colleagues (2014) suggest an increase in device sampling frequency would limit the magnitude of error during high-speed COD. Despite this, the results of this present study found PM to underestimate peak acceleration during both linear acceleration and acceleration following a change of direction. On the other hand, Sandmæl & Dalen (2023) and Waldron *et al.* (2021) both report PM to overestimate total and peak accelerations compared to GPS, which Waldron and colleagues describe to be related to the higher raw sampling rate of PM (1000 Hz). This suggests PM can measure more high intensity velocity changes compared to GPS which would align with the literature which demonstrates 10 Hz GPS to be a valid means of measuring acceleration, however the validity is reduced when at higher velocities (Scott *et al.*, 2016). Waldron and colleagues also determine PM can record rapid changes in velocities which GPS would be unable to measure, however, the results in this study show GPS to overestimate peak acceleration which is conflicting with this determination and suggests further research is needed. This is further supported by moderate to poor CV ratings, meaning PM's validity for measuring peak acceleration is still unclear. As both PM and GPS were set to measure accelerations at the same threshold ($>2 \text{ m/s}^2$), this would suggest the difference between devices may be related to the methods of testing used. Waldron and colleagues (2021) measured accelerations during the SAFT90 protocol which is a fatigue inducing continuous running drill. Due to the nature of this test, the velocity and intensity which the test will be performed will gradually decrease throughout the protocol and hence may result in a difference between devices when measuring peak accelerations. Meanwhile, within this study, peak acceleration measured during the 5 m sprint displayed moderate validity whereas both 505 left and right showed poor validity. One possibility for this difference in validity between tests may be related to the need to decelerate and turn during the 505 while the 5 m sprint is purely a linear acceleration. This again may influence the velocity of the acceleration from which the differences in sampling frequency between devices may affect the outcome measures. In addition, anatomical placement should be considered as a factor for measuring acceleration. As PM is positioned closer to the point of contact with the ground, it could be hypothesized this device may be more effective for determining ground contact and acceleration than GPS. Although Horsley *et al.* (2021) found no significance difference between devices positioned on the foot compared to being placed on the upper back for measures of running gait analysis. Further research is required to determine PMs ability to record peak acceleration and the influence sampling frequency and test protocol has on outcome parameters.

5.3 Peak Deceleration

As for peak acceleration, the results for peak deceleration show significant differences between devices. Peak deceleration was measured during the deceleration phase of both the 505 left and right and found PM to significantly underestimate peak deceleration in both tests. Poor validity was shown for deceleration relating to both 505 left and right with a CV of 13.93% and 13.69% respectively. These results are supported by the findings from Myhill *et al.* (2022) who found PM to underestimate peak acceleration against a 3D motion system and reported an average underestimation of $-0.214 \pm 0.787 \text{ m/s}^2$ with a maximal underestimation of 3.48 m/s^2 . As with peak acceleration, the authors suggest validity decreases with an increase in velocity and dependant on the exercise performed. This suggestion is also supported by Alanen *et al.* (2020) and Ghattas & Jarvis (2021) who also suggest the IMU validity decreases at higher velocities and during high-speed decelerations. Conversely, the findings of this present study do not support the results of Waldron and Colleagues (2021) who found PM consistently overestimated peak decelerations against 3 separate GPS devices.

The findings from this present study would suggest PM is not as valid for measuring high speed actions like rapid decelerations compared to GPS. As previously suggested, this may be a result of the significant difference in sampling frequencies between PM and GPS. As reported by Waldron and colleagues (2021), PM has been suggested to measure high speed velocity changes which would be undetectable by GPS and thus would suggest an increase in outcome accuracy for PM. However, as GPS has been proven both valid and reliable for measuring high-speed decelerations (Varley *et al.*, 2012), and PM has been shown to underestimate this during this present study, further research is required to clarify how the difference in sampling frequencies affects the performance outcomes of the devices. The differences in testing protocols between studies may also impact results as mentioned in peak acceleration. Both devices were set to measure decelerations at the same threshold ($> -2 \text{ m/s}^2$), however Waldron *et al.* (2021) measured peak deceleration during the SAFT90 protocol where decelerations may have been performed at a lower/or higher intensity which have not been measured by GPS due to its limited sampling rate. It is also unclear which portion of the protocol, Waldron and colleagues (2021) used to measure deceleration. It could be assumed deceleration was measured at the end of the 20 m sprint as deceleration is required to change direction to continue the test. Due to the continuous nature of the protocol, participants may not have achieved full speed and may have decelerated more gradually before reaching the end of the 20 m which would affect findings. On the other hand, if the participants were able to reach a high velocity during the 20 m sprint, the intensity of the deceleration would be greater than the shorter 505 test used in the present study. This would also highlight the potential effect of the different

sampling rates between devices as PM would be able to record the greater deceleration velocity which GPS may be unable to detect. The difference in testing protocols will likely have the largest effect on the outcomes of this study as GPS validity has been shown to be reduced when changing direction at high speeds (Rawstorn *et al.*, 2014; Scott *et al.*, 2016), meanwhile IMU research is limited in terms of measuring change of direction at high speeds. Despite this limited research, Alanen *et al.* (2020) concluded that IMUs could identify COD events with acceptable validity, however, results were unreliable and generally overestimated measures associated with COD movement, such as forces, accelerations, and decelerations. Although these conclusions do not directly support the findings within this current study, they do emphasise the inconsistency between research papers surrounding IMUs ability to measure peak deceleration with good validity.

Despite the findings of this research not agreeing with Waldron *et al.* (2021), Sandmæl & Dalen (2023) reported PM recorded a significantly overestimated the number of decelerations than GPS which although not directly relating to peak deceleration supports Waldron and colleagues (2021) findings. This also aligns with Waldron and colleagues' suggestion that PM can record rapid changes in velocities which GPS would be unable to measure. However, as the results of this study found PM to underestimate peak deceleration, and Waldron *et al.* (2021) found PM to overestimate, this would suggest PM validity for measuring peak deceleration in football cannot be concluded and further investigation is required. This research should look to use the same protocols as performed within this study, to be able to compare findings to confirm PM validity.

5.4 Total Distance

During the 1 km TT both devices measured a lower absolute total distance compared to the measured distance of 1000 m, however PM reported a significantly lower total distance compared with GPS, with an average underestimation of 2.35%. Despite results finding PM to underestimate total distance, PM provided good validity for measuring total distance with a CV of 1.36%. These results correlate with the findings reported by Sandmæl & Dalen (2023). The author's findings are comparable to this study as they similarly reported PM to underestimate total distance but still display good validity. These findings are further supported by Sandmæl, Tillard & Dalen (2023) who found PM to significantly underestimate total distance during a rectangular running protocol compared to the measured course distance. As these authors have reported PM to underestimate speed and distance at higher velocities, the changes in speed during this protocol would affect PM's ability to measure distance covered. Furthermore, research from Dasa *et al.* (2022) found PM to underestimate total distance during an intermittent running protocol, however, the authors determine PM was closer to the actual course distance compared to GPS.

The results displayed in this present study, Sandmæl & Dalen (2023), and Sandmæl, Tillard & Dalen (2023) are not consistent with Waldron and colleagues (2021) who found PM to consistently overestimate total distances with an average error of 25–50 m against GPS. The opposite findings are reported within this study, and the difference in results may be related to the difference in running velocities involved in the various tests across these studies. Despite increased velocity during initial acceleration, as well as accelerations and decelerations involved during each turn, total distance was measured at lower velocities during the 1 km TT performed within this research and during the SRP investigated by Sandmæl & Dalen (2023). However, higher total distance measured by PM was reported by Sandmæl & Dalen (2023) during small-sided games and by Waldron and colleagues during SAFT90 which may relate to distance being covered in higher velocity zones in which GPS reliability has been shown to be reduced (Scott *et al.*, 2016). This would suggest the testing protocol chosen to measure total distance will influence the results. This is a key area which could be investigated in future studies where researchers can measure total distance measured during different velocity zones, which will determine whether higher or lower velocity zones will significantly influence PM's ability to accurately record total distance covered. As the findings for peak acceleration and peak deceleration are inconclusive within the current literature for determining PM validity, it could be suggested that the SAFT90 protocol used by Waldron and colleagues (2021) may be an unsuitable test for measuring total distance. This is due to the various high intensity changes of direction and number of accelerations & decelerations performed over short distances, which if underestimated will affect PM ability to effectively measure total distance. Total distance may be influenced by the ability of the participants foot to be directly under GPS whilst turning, this should be considered as the accuracy of hitting the line absolutely is unclear. This may result in accumulative error which could affect the validity of the results. Regardless of this, these results would suggest PM to measure total distance with good validity as suggested by Waldron and colleagues (2021) and Sandmæl & Dalen (2023), despite being shown to underestimate total distance compared to GPS as the criterion method. Anatomical placement, and internal device technology may influence data output and will largely explain differences found between PM and GPS. As GPS is aligned with the body's centre of mass and PM is positioned on the lower limbs, this may cause variation in movement detection which will impact distance measured (Barrett *et al.*, 2014). However, due to the questions raised over PM ability to record total distance when running at different velocity zones, PM validity cannot be concluded, and further investigation is required.

5.5 Limitations

This research is not without its limitations. Firstly, the effect of anatomical placement of the devices is unclear, however literature suggests device placement can influence results (Barret *et al.*, 2014). As GPS was placed on the participants upper back and PM was positioned on each foot, the difference in measurement accuracy between these two sites is unclear. As PM is positioned closer to the point of contact with the ground, this may be better suited to measure aspects relating to speed and acceleration, however, this cannot be confirmed from the literature (Horsley *et al.*, 2021). The placement of GPS on the upper back has been shown to be valid and reliable for measuring human motion at all speeds as it is closer to the body centre of mass and can detect motion of the trunk (McLellan *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, as PM is placed on the foot, the ability of PM to sit directly under GPS during COD movements such as turning on the line during the 1 km TT is unknown. This could result in accumulative error of distance being recorded and should be considered as a limitation of this test. This limitation could be mitigated by using poles for players to run around which would reduce any error from players not touching the line, or tracking devices not being aligned at the point of turn. Additionally, the use of different performance tests from those used in the original research from Waldron and colleagues (2021) may impact results. This study opted to utilise performance tests commonly used to measure physical characteristics within football, meanwhile previous research used a football specific simulation test (SAFT90) which tries to replicate the intermittent running nature of football. Although there are different protocols used between studies making direct comparisons challenging, the testing protocols utilised within this research may be more suitable in measuring PM validity due to being more time efficient, repeatable, and have been proven valid for measuring performance in football (Altmann *et al.*, 2019; Ryan *et al.*, 2021). Despite this, the lack of available research surrounding PM and IMUs in football makes determining validity difficult as there is not enough evidence to support these findings. Therefore, this research opens the door for further investigation into the validity of PM for use in elite female football.

5.6 Practical Implications and Future Considerations

As the findings from this research were unable to conclusively determine the validity of PM for measuring the key performance measures in football, further investigation is required. Since the validity of these devices remains unclear, this raises questions about their use in training and game situations as it would appear unable to cope with the high intensity demands of elite football. Data monitoring is an asset to elite sports teams, the uncertain measurement accuracy of these devices should be considered before use and before distributing data to players and coaches.

The findings within this research, supported by that of Sandmæl & Dalen (2023), suggests PM can be used to effectively measure distance covered in team sports. However, the findings of this current research would imply caution should be taken by practitioners when monitoring high-speed actions involving accelerations, decelerations, as poor validity was reported within this research and requires further investigation before PM may be used with confidence in an elite sport setting.

Future research should look expand upon this study and previous literature to determine the concurrent validity of PM to measure high intensity running actions in football such as linear sprinting and high-speed changes of direction. This research ideally will combine methods used from previous literature specifically regarding performance tests applied and tracking devices used. Future investigations would benefit from investigating PM validity during a graded exercise test and competitive match play as this will confirm its validity for measuring key physical performance metrics during competitive matches. These future investigations may also wish to utilise a GPS with a higher sampling rate to minimise the difference in measuring frequencies between devices. Furthermore, other technologies may be used such as 3D motion systems as utilised by Myhill *et al.* (2022) which would increase the strength of the literature for measuring the validity of PM.

Chapter 6: Conclusions

This study measured the validity of the PM IMU to measure key physical performance metrics in elite female football. The findings within this study suggested PM to have good validity when measuring total distance, moderate to poor validity for peak acceleration, and poor validity for peak velocity and peak deceleration. These findings are inconsistent with previous literature, highlighting the need for further investigation, particularly for measuring high-speed actions which are critical to football performance. Overall, the validity of the PM IMU in football performance remains inconclusive and requires further research. Future investigations should look to standardise the validation protocol for PM as the use of various assessment methods within the current literature has yielded inconsistent results.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Medical Questionnaire

Medical Questionnaire for Physiological Testing

Before any physiological tests are carried on you, we will have to check whether you are in a satisfactory condition to undergo strenuous exercise. We would therefore like you to fill in the following questionnaire about yourself. All information will be treated as strictly confidential.

Name _____

Date of Birth ____/____/____

Specialist Sport (if any) _____

Male

Female

PLEASE TICK ONE ANSWER ONLY

1. Have you ever had a heart attack, coronary revascularisation surgery or a stroke?

No Yes

2. Has your doctor ever told you that you have heart trouble or vascular disease?

No Yes

3. Has your doctor ever told you that you have a heart murmur?

No Yes

4. Do you ever suffer from pains in your chest, especially with exercise?

No Yes

5. Do you ever get pains in your calves, buttocks or at the back of your legs during exercise which are not due to soreness or stiffness?

No Yes

6. Do you ever feel faint or have spells of severe dizziness, particularly with exercise?

No Yes

7. Do you experience swelling or accumulation of fluid about the ankles?

No Yes

8. Do you ever get the feeling that your heart is suddenly beating faster, racing or skipping beats, either at rest or during exercise?

No **Yes**

9. Do you have chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, interstitial lung disease, or cystic fibrosis?

No **Yes**

10. Have you ever had an attack of shortness of breath that developed when you were not doing anything strenuous, at any time in the last 12 months?

No **Yes**

11. Have you ever had an attack of shortness of breath that developed after you stopped exercising, at any time in the last 12 months?

No **Yes**

12. Have you ever been woken at night by an attack of shortness of breath, at any time in the last 12 months?

No **Yes**

13. Do you have diabetes [Type I (Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM)) or Type II (non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM))]? If so, do you have trouble controlling your diabetes?

No **Yes**

14. Do you have any ulcerated wounds or cuts on your feet that do not seem to heal?

No **Yes**

15. Do you have any liver, kidney or thyroid disorders?

No **Yes**

16. Do you experience unusual fatigue or shortness of breath with usual activities?

No **Yes**

17. Is there any other physical reason or medical condition, or are you taking any medication(s) which could prevent you from undertaking an exercise program, or that you are concerned about? If so, please explain.*(see notes)

No **Yes**

18. Have you ever suffered from a viral infection in the last two weeks?

No **Yes**

* NOTES: Some of these conditions might include a history of blood clotting, osteoporosis, bone fractures or serious musculoskeletal disorders, or if they have recently lost a weight without trying to. Other types of conditions might include psychiatric disorders, later-stage pregnancy or those with a history of health problems during pregnancy. Those people taking medication(s) for medical conditions listed may also need medical clearance.

I have read, understood and completed this questionnaire. Any questions I had were answered to my full satisfaction. If there will be a change of status to any of the conditions above I will inform the researcher or the senior academic involved IMMEDIATELY.

NAME _____ SIGNATURE _____ DATE ___/___/_____

References: (1) Sports Medicine Australia (SMA) pre-exercise screening system 2005, Australian Government, Department of Health and Ageing (2) American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) (2000). ACSM's guidelines for exercise testing and prescription (6th ed). New York, Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. (3) Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) (2004). Heart, stroke and vascular diseases Australian facts 2004. Canberra, AIHW and National Heart Foundation of Australia. (4) National Heart Foundation (NHF) (2005). Physical activity recommendations for people with cardiovascular disease. Sydney, National Heart Foundation of Australia. (5) Olds, T. and Norton, K. (1999). Pre-exercise health screening guide. Champaign, Ill, Human Kinetics.

UWS Sport and Exercise Laboratories Screening Flow Chart

To be completed by test supervisor:	
<u>MUST BE SIGNED BEFORE THE SUBJECT STARTS EXERCISE</u>	
Checked by _____	Signed _____
Date ____/____/____	

Written Consent Form

Title of Project: Determine the validity and reliability of foot mounted Inertial measurement units in measuring external load metrics in elite female footballers.

Name of Researcher: Mark Wright

Please initial box

1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

3 I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of person taking consent (if different from researcher):

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Date: